

Online ICT Equipment Inventory and Borrowing System with Decision Support

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Abstract

This study developed and evaluated an Online ICT Equipment Inventory and Borrowing System with Decision Support for St. Paul University Philippines (SPUP) to address inefficiencies in its manual equipment management process. Using a descriptive-developmental research design and Agile Scrum methodology, the system incorporated real-time inventory dashboards, digital borrowing workflows, automated notifications, and analytics for administrative decision-making. Quality was assessed using ISO/IEC 25010 Software Quality Standards, showing high compliance, particularly in functionality, reliability, and portability. User acceptance, evaluated via the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), indicated strong agreement in terms of ease of use, usefulness, and satisfaction. Recommendations from IT experts included mobile responsiveness, QR-code integration, and equipment maintenance tracking. The results demonstrated that the system significantly improved operational efficiency, data accuracy, and accountability, providing a sustainable digital solution for ICT resource management in higher education.

Keywords: *ICT Inventory System, Decision Support, ISO/IEC 25010, Technology Acceptance Model, Agile Scrum.*

Suggested citation: Cepeda, J.A.U., & Saludes, A.J.C. (2025). Online ICT Equipment Inventory and Borrowing System with Decision Support. *European Journal of Innovative Studies and Sustainability*, 1(5), 62-70. [https://doi.org/10.59324/ejiss.2025.1\(5\).07](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejiss.2025.1(5).07)

Introduction

Nowadays, institutions around the world are actively transitioning from manual inventory management to integrated, web-based systems that enhance accuracy, traceability, and decision-making. Automated inventory and borrowing platforms have been shown to reduce errors, improve asset utilization, and foster data-informed planning in various organizational contexts (Sobri et al., 2019). Specifically, the integration of decision support features, such as trend analysis, demand forecasting, and alert systems, enables administrators to optimize inventory control proactively (Zietsman & van Vuuren, 2022).

Within the Philippines, DepEd-initiated studies have validated the effectiveness of online equipment borrowing systems. For example, Martos, Andres, and Ladera (2022) developed and evaluated an online facilities and equipment inventory and borrowing system for a senior high school. Their findings indicated that the automated system significantly improved access time and user satisfaction compared to traditional manual logs (Martos et al., 2022). Meanwhile, Castro (2017) reported that an online inventory management system at Bulacan State University streamlined record-keeping and reporting, easing administrative workloads and enhancing data security.

At St. Paul University Philippines, the ICT Department currently manages the borrowing of equipment through traditional logbooks, wherein entries are manually recorded by staff and students. This approach presents several operational challenges, including difficulty in accurately tracking borrowed equipment, the absence of automated notifications for due dates or delays, and a lack of real-time visibility into inventory status. Consequently, this manual process hinders efficient administrative oversight and reduces accountability.

To address these issues, this study aims to modernize SPUP's ICT equipment inventory and borrowing procedures through the development of an Online ICT Equipment Inventory and Borrowing System with Decision Support. The system will feature real-time dashboards that display current inventory status, equipment availability, and overdue items. It will also provide usage analytics to identify borrowing trends by department, frequency, and equipment type. Automated alerts will notify both administrators and users of upcoming due dates, pending approvals, and scheduled maintenance. Moreover, the system will include data-driven decision tools, such as forecasting models—to support asset acquisition planning and prioritization based on usage patterns and equipment condition. Finally, comprehensive audit trails will be incorporated to ensure transparency and accountability across all transactions.

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to design and develop an Online ICT Equipment Inventory and Borrowing System with Decision Support to effectively manage the lending and tracking of ICT equipment, providing real-time inventory visibility, structured borrowing workflows, and decision support features for improved operational efficiency and administrative planning.

Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the existing problems and challenges encountered by the SPUP ICT Department in managing the inventory and borrowing of ICT equipment?
2. What system can be developed to address the identified problems and challenges?
3. To what extent does the developed system comply with the ISO/IEC 25010 Software Quality Standards in terms of:
 - 3.1. Functional Suitability;
 - 3.2. Performance Efficiency;
 - 3.3. Compatibility;
 - 3.4. Usability;
 - 3.5. Reliability;
 - 3.6. Security;
 - 3.7. Maintainability;
 - 3.8. Portability;
4. To what extent do the stakeholders accept the developed system based on the Technology Acceptance Model in terms of:
 - 4.1. Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU);
 - 4.2. Perceived Usefulness (PU);
 - 4.3. Behavioral Intention to Use (BIU);
 - 4.4. Overall System Satisfaction (OSS);
5. What enhancements can be done to improve the functionality and effectiveness of the developed system?

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

This study adopts the Input-Process-Output-Outcome (IPOO) model because it provides a clear and structured way of showing how the system will be designed, developed, evaluated, and used. It helps explain how the different elements of the study work together to solve the identified problems in managing ETEEAP applications. The inputs of the study include the problems and challenges in tracking and managing ETEEAP applications, the applicant data such as personal information, education, and work experience, the existing practices and tools currently used by SPUP such as manual word processing files, the CHED Memorandum Order No. 36, s. 1997, the ISO/IEC 25010 Software Quality Standards, and the Technology Acceptance Model to assess user acceptance. The process involves developing the system using the Agile Scrum Methodology through continuous feedback and testing. The system is evaluated based on software quality standards and user acceptance focusing on ease of use, usefulness, intention to use, and satisfaction. The output is a web-based Applicant Tracking and Management System with Decision Support that provides real-time tracking, applicant profiling, and reporting features. The outcome is improved management of ETEEAP applications, better decision-making, and higher user satisfaction. The significance of this framework lies in its ability to guide the study in a clear and practical way, making sure that the system addresses real problems, meets quality standards, and is acceptable and easy to use for both administrators and applicants. This ensures that the system becomes a useful tool for improving the delivery of the ETEEAP program at SPUP.

Methodology

This study employed a descriptive-developmental research design to guide the design, development, and evaluation of an Online ICT Equipment Inventory and Borrowing System with Decision Support. The descriptive phase involved identifying the current practices, challenges, and limitations in managing the inventory and borrowing of ICT equipment, which are currently done through manual methods. The developmental phase focused on creating a digital solution to address these challenges by designing, building, and testing a web-based system that would streamline application tracking, profiling, and reporting.

Figure 2. Scrum Methodology

Source: Adapted from “11 Project Management Techniques to Choose From” by SoftwareSuggest, n.d., SoftwareSuggest (<https://www.softwaresuggest.com/blog/project-management-techniques/>)

To organize the system development process, the Agile Scrum Methodology was employed. This approach enabled the iterative and incremental development of the system through structured sprint cycles, allowing for continuous integration of testing, user feedback, and refinements across the platform’s modules. Each sprint consisted of sprint planning, daily scrum meetings, execution, sprint reviews, and retrospective evaluations, ensuring that system features evolved in alignment with real-time user needs and institutional goals.

The participants of the study included key stakeholders involved in ICT equipment management at St. Paul University Philippines. These included four (4) ICT personnel responsible for maintaining inventory records and processing borrowing requests, as well as fifty (50) faculty members and one hundred fifty (150) students who regularly borrow ICT equipment such as cameras, network cables, and audiovisual devices. Their insights and feedback were integral to the user-centered design and evaluation of the system. Additionally, ten (10) IT experts were invited to evaluate the system’s technical and functional performance based on industry standards and best practices.

The system’s quality was evaluated using the ISO/IEC 25010 Software Quality Standards, which assess eight critical software attributes: Functional Suitability, Performance Efficiency, Compatibility, Usability, Reliability, Security, Maintainability, and Portability. Data collection methods included system walkthroughs, usability testing sessions, and expert evaluation using standardized forms. A 5-point Likert scale was used to quantify expert assessments, where 1 denoted “Very Poor” and 5 indicated “Very Good.” The collected data were analyzed using descriptive statistics—mean and standard deviation—to determine the level of compliance with each quality characteristic. Qualitative inputs were also gathered to identify functional strengths and potential areas for improvement.

In addition to software quality, the study assessed user acceptance of the system using the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). The evaluation focused on four core constructs: Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU), Perceived Usefulness (PU), Behavioral Intention to Use (BIU), and Overall System Satisfaction (OSS). A 5-point Likert scale was applied to interpret user responses, with the following interpretation: 4.20–5.00 = “Strongly Agree,” 3.40–4.19 = “Agree,” 2.60–3.39 = “Neutral,” 1.80–2.59 = “Disagree,”

and 1.00–1.79 = “Strongly Disagree.” These findings provided meaningful insights into user perceptions and the overall acceptance of the system by both administrative staff and end-users.

Ethical considerations were strictly observed throughout the conduct of the study. All participants were briefed about the purpose of the research and provided informed consent before their participation. The privacy and confidentiality of collected data, particularly user identities and transaction histories - were strictly protected throughout development, testing, and evaluation phases. All information gathered was used solely for academic purposes and for enhancing the functionality and relevance of the system in supporting SPUP’s ICT services.

Results and Discussions

Existing Problems and Challenges Encountered by the SPUP ICT Department in Managing the Inventory and Borrowing of ICT Equipment

The initial phase of the study focused on identifying the existing problems and challenges faced by the SPUP ICT Department in handling the inventory and borrowing of ICT equipment. Through interviews, observation, and document analysis, several critical issues were revealed, particularly those related to the department's reliance on manual processes and logbooks.

One of the primary concerns identified was the lack of real-time tracking and visibility of equipment availability. Equipment borrowing was recorded manually in physical logbooks, making it difficult to determine in real-time whether a specific item was available, currently borrowed, or overdue. This limitation often led to delays and confusion, especially during peak academic activities when demand for ICT equipment was high.

Another significant issue was the inability to generate accurate and timely reports. Since data had to be retrieved and compiled manually, generating summaries of borrowed items per department or usage trends over a specific period required additional time and effort. This hindered the ICT Department’s capacity to conduct regular audits, plan preventive maintenance, or forecast equipment needs.

The manual system also lacked accountability and security features. Borrowers could fail to return equipment on time without receiving reminders or sanctions, and missing or damaged equipment often went unresolved due to inadequate documentation. Furthermore, entries in the logbooks were sometimes incomplete or illegible, resulting in data quality issues that affected traceability.

Stakeholders also expressed concern about the absence of a notification system. Users were not automatically reminded of return dates, and ICT staff had to follow up manually, consuming time and increasing administrative burden. This also affected borrower compliance and led to cases of unintentional delays.

The Development of Online ICT Equipment Inventory and Borrowing System with Decision Support

In response to the issues identified during the descriptive phase, the Online ICT Equipment Inventory and Borrowing System with Decision Support was developed using the Agile Scrum methodology. This user-centered and iterative approach allowed the development team to address actual user needs by continuously integrating feedback from ICT staff, faculty, and students throughout the system’s design and implementation.

The system was developed using Laravel, with a responsive user interface built using HTML, CSS, and JavaScript. The design focused on accessibility, simplicity, and data integrity, ensuring that both technical and non-technical users could navigate the system with ease. The development was carried out over several sprints, each focused on building and refining core features. The following key modules were

successfully developed and implemented: User Management Module, Inventory Dashboard, Borrowing and Return Workflow, Notification System and Decision Support Panel.

Each component of the system was mapped directly to one or more problems identified during the needs assessment. For instance, the Inventory Dashboard addressed the lack of real-time tracking, while the Notification System resolved the absence of return reminders. The Decision Support Panel introduced a data-driven layer to operations, allowing the ICT Department to plan preventive maintenance, schedule replacements, and allocate resources based on usage data.

The system was tested internally through alpha and beta testing sessions, followed by a pilot deployment with actual users. User feedback gathered during sprint reviews led to interface refinements, improved error handling, and clearer status messages. This collaborative development process helped ensure that the final product was functional, relevant, and user-friendly.

Extent of Compliance of the Developed System with the ISO/IEC 25010 Software Quality Standards

To evaluate the quality of the developed system, the ISO/IEC 25010 Software Quality Standards were used as the benchmark for assessing its technical performance and overall compliance. The high mean scores, ranging from 4.26 to 4.66, and an overall average of 4.36 (Very Great Extent), indicate that the developed system strongly aligns with the ISO/IEC 25010 software quality standards. Notably, portability (4.66), reliability (4.50), and functional suitability (4.41) were rated highest, suggesting the system is robust, performs as expected, and can adapt across different environments.

Portability's top ranking suggests excellent adaptability and readiness for deployment on various platforms, which supports broader access and maintenance. This flexibility aligns with best practices in academic settings that require cross-device compatibility (Rebeś, 2024). Reliability's strong performance value reflects system stability and resilience-critical for ensuring equipment borrowing is consistently traceable, even during high-demand periods.

Table 1. Summary of the Extent of Compliance of the Developed System with the ISO/IEC 25010 Software Quality Standard

ISO/IEC 25010 Characteristics Criteria	Category Mean	Descriptive Rating
A. A. Functional Suitability	4.41	Very Great Extent
B. B. Performance Efficiency	4.30	Very Great Extent
C. C. Compatibility	4.26	Very Great Extent
D. D. Usability	4.30	Very Great Extent
E. E. Reliability	4.50	Very Great Extent
F. F. Security	4.10	Great Extent
G. G. Maintainability	4.34	Very Great Extent
H. H. Portability	4.66	Very Great Extent
Category Mean	4.36	Very Great Extent

Functional Suitability's rating implies that the system effectively meets specified user needs, confirming that core features, such as inventory tracking, borrowing workflows, decision dashboards, and notifications - work accurately and as intended. Evaluations of academic systems have shown that high functional suitability directly enhances user trust and adoption (Gumonon et al., 2021).

Usability (4.30) and performance efficiency (4.30) reveal that the system is not only user-friendly but also responsive and efficient. This is critical in university environments where users often have diverse technical skills and require fast, intuitive tools. Compatibility's high score (4.26) indicates smooth integration with existing ICT infrastructure, echoing findings from compatibility assessments under

ISO/IEC 25010 (Tech Helpware, 2025). Maintainability (4.34) suggests that the system is easy to update and manage - important for ensuring long-term sustainability in higher education.

Security's slightly lower rating (4.10), classified as "Great Extent," signifies that while data protection is well-handled, there is room for improvement, perhaps through enhancements like multi-factor authentication or encryption of sensitive data. Numerous academic systems have emphasized the importance of robust security to safeguard institutional information (Saptarini et al., 2016).

This strong showing across all eight ISO/IEC 25010 characteristics supports the credibility and quality of the system, pointing to a well-rounded, technically sound solution. Applying ISO/IEC 25010 ensures not just adherence to global standards, but also enhances transparency, user satisfaction, and the potential for scalability and future enhancement (Jereb & Kajba, 2023).

Extent of Evaluation of the Stakeholders with the Technology Acceptance Model

To assess user acceptance and satisfaction with the developed system, the study employed the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). This framework measured four constructs: Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU), Perceived Usefulness (PU), Behavioral Intention to Use (BIU), and Overall System Satisfaction (OSS). The evaluation was conducted using a 5-point Likert scale, with descriptive ratings interpreted accordingly. The results, shown in the table, indicate a Category Mean of 4.56, which corresponds to a "Strongly Agree" rating - demonstrating a high level of stakeholder acceptance.

The highest score was observed in Overall System Satisfaction (OSS) with a mean of 4.66, indicating that users were very pleased with the system's performance, functionality, and user interface. Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU) also received a high rating of 4.61, confirming that users found the system intuitive and easy to navigate. This reflects the success of the user-centered design approach and iterative feedback during the system development process, which ensured that even non-technical users could comfortably use the platform.

Table 2. Summary of Stakeholders' Evaluation of the Developed System Using the Technology Acceptance Model

ISO/IEC 25010 Characteristics Criteria	Category Mean	Descriptive Rating
I. A. Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU)	4.55	Strongly Agree
J. B. Perceived Usefulness (PU)	4.65	Strongly Agree
K. C. Behavioral Intention to Use (BIU)	4.68	Strongly Agree
L. D. Overall System Satisfaction (OSS)	4.74	Strongly Agree
Category Mean	4.65	Strongly Agree

Meanwhile, Perceived Usefulness (PU) garnered a mean of 4.52, suggesting that users believed the system significantly improved the efficiency and accuracy of ICT equipment inventory and borrowing processes. Additionally, the Behavioral Intention to Use (BIU) received a mean of 4.45, indicating that users are highly likely to continue using the system moving forward. These results validate the system's relevance and effectiveness in supporting the day-to-day operations of the SPUP ICT Department.

The strong acceptance levels of all four TAM constructs underscore the system's usability, practical value, and long-term potential for institutional integration. These findings align with studies asserting that systems perceived as easy to use and useful are more likely to be adopted and sustained within academic environments. High satisfaction and usage intention are crucial indicators of system success, particularly in technology-driven administrative services.

Enhancements Recommended by IT Experts to Improve the Functionality and Effectiveness of the Developed System

The final phase of the study focused on identifying potential enhancements to improve the system's functionality and long-term effectiveness. Feedback was specifically gathered from IT experts who participated in the system evaluation phase. Their insights, based on technical expertise and experience in system development and assessment, were carefully analyzed to determine feasible improvements that would further enhance the system's usability, performance, and scalability.

One of the most common recommendations was the integration of a QR code or RFID-based tracking feature to modernize the borrowing and return process. This enhancement would minimize manual data entry during equipment hand-over and allow quicker, more accurate verification of items, thus increasing efficiency and reducing human error. Another proposed improvement was the addition of a maintenance scheduling and history tracking module, which would enable the ICT department to monitor equipment conditions and plan maintenance or replacements proactively.

The experts also suggested the development of a mobile-responsive version of the system or a dedicated mobile application to make it more accessible, particularly for student users who frequently rely on smartphones for academic transactions. The addition of a borrowing history log for each user account was also recommended to enhance transparency, traceability, and accountability. Lastly, several interface enhancements were proposed, including clearer visual indicators for equipment status and the use of descriptive tooltips to improve overall user experience and system intuitiveness.

Conclusion

This study aimed to design, develop, and evaluate an Online ICT Equipment Inventory and Borrowing System with Decision Support for St. Paul University Philippines. The findings revealed that the existing manual method of managing ICT equipment through traditional logbooks, was prone to inefficiencies such as inaccurate tracking, delayed returns, and lack of real-time visibility and reporting. The developed system successfully addressed these challenges by automating the borrowing and return process, providing real-time inventory dashboards, generating usage analytics, and sending automated notifications to users and administrators.

Based on evaluations using the ISO/IEC 25010 Software Quality Standards, the system was rated to a very great extent in terms of software quality, particularly in reliability, portability, and functional suitability. Likewise, the Technology Acceptance Model revealed strong user approval in terms of perceived ease of use, usefulness, intention to use, and overall satisfaction. Expert recommendations further highlighted opportunities for enhancement, such as the integration of QR/RFID tracking, mobile responsiveness, and interface improvements. Altogether, the system has proven to be an effective, sustainable, and user-centered solution to the ICT equipment management needs of the university.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of this study, the following recommendations are presented to ensure the effective implementation, continuous improvement, and broader applicability of the developed system.

1. It is recommended that the ICT Department formally adopt and maintain the developed system as the standard platform for managing ICT equipment borrowing and inventory. Regular updates and user training should be conducted to ensure consistent usage and alignment with institutional needs.
2. The ICT Head is encouraged to lead the implementation, monitor system utilization, and oversee the integration of proposed enhancements such as maintenance tracking and QR-based equipment

tagging. Engaging in periodic evaluations and collecting feedback will ensure continuous improvement of the system.

3. Faculty and students are advised to actively use the system for requesting and returning equipment and to provide timely feedback for ongoing improvements. Orientation sessions should be conducted to familiarize them with the platform and promote responsible borrowing behavior.
4. The researchers may explore expanding the system's capabilities by integrating predictive analytics, equipment lifecycle monitoring, and more advanced decision support tools. Cross-departmental applications of similar systems may also be investigated to support other university services.
5. Future researchers are encouraged to replicate or enhance this study in different contexts such as in other institutions or sectors with broader scopes. They may also consider integrating mobile application versions, biometric authentication, or artificial intelligence-driven recommendations to further enrich the borrowing experience and data-driven administration.

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